

Alumni Unified Management and Network Information System

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Abstract

This paper discusses the design and development of the ALumni Unified Management and Network Information System, a comprehensive platform designed to strengthen connections between alumni and their alma mater, fostering lifelong relationships and opportunities. The application enables alumni to maintain a dynamic connection with their academic institution and peers through features such as personalized profiles, networking tools, event management, mentorship opportunities, and exclusive career resources. By integrating user-friendly technology, the platform allows graduates to access and contribute to a global community, promoting professional growth and personal development. Developed thru a combination of web tools, including PHP, Laravel frameworks, CSS3 and HTML5, the MySQL-database-driven project is currently deployed via alumni/csuaparri.net. The ALUMNI App features a synchronized profile management for the alumni of CSU Aparri, a usable and functional role-based dashboards, analytics dashboard for Alumni Coordinators, profile verification module, module for the assessment of the relevance and applicability of current employment, module for the assessment of the school and related factors, a module for the updating and management of the employment data, push notification module for alumni, and news or updates module. This application not only celebrates the achievements of alumni but also nurtures a sense of belonging, enhancing the overall value of the alumni network for individuals and institutions alike.

Keywords: Alumni, employment, connections, network, career resources.

1. Introduction

An alumnus, in the context of education, refers to individuals who have graduated from a particular institution, such as a school, college, or university. These individuals, collectively known as alumni, share a common bond through their educational experiences and affiliation with the institution. Tracking alumni offers numerous benefits to educational institutions. Firstly, it allows for the cultivation of a strong and interconnected network of former students, fostering a sense of community and providing valuable opportunities for mentorship and professional networking. This network becomes a valuable resource for current students seeking guidance and support in their career development. Additionally, alumni tracking serves as a vital tool for fundraising efforts, as institutions can engage with successful graduates to garner financial support for scholarships, facilities, and other initiatives.

The ability to showcase the achievements and success stories of alumni enhances the CSU reputation, attracting prospective students and donors. The data gathered from alumni tracking also provides valuable insights for institutional improvement, helping to refine educational programs and adapt to the evolving needs of the job market. By offering continuous learning opportunities and maintaining engagement through events and communication, CSU can ensure that their alumni remain connected and involved long after graduation, contributing to the ongoing success and development of the educational community.

Implementing an alumnus tracking system poses several challenges for educational institutions. One significant hurdle is the dynamic nature of alumni contact information; individuals frequently change addresses, phone numbers, and emails, making it challenging to maintain accurate records. Privacy concerns also emerge as a critical challenge, as institutions must navigate the delicate balance between tracking alumni for engagement purposes and respecting privacy regulations. Limited resources, both in terms of personnel and technology, can impede the establishment of an effective tracking system. Encouraging active participation and engagement from a diverse alumni population, especially those who may have graduated years ago, presents another challenge. Additionally, there may be resistance from alumni who perceive tracking as invasive or have reservations about how their data will be used. Overcoming these challenges requires a thoughtful and strategic approach that prioritizes privacy, invests in robust tracking infrastructure, and effectively communicates the value proposition of alumni tracking to both the institution and its graduates.

Electronic and Online systems is a crucial initiative of the Cagayan State University designed to address specific needs and other challenges met by its stakeholders, particularly its residents. By providing an electronic system, the university gains access to ready information, streamline service delivery, bridge the digital gap, address the gaps of faulty and unclear records kept in the Alumni and Relations Affairs Offices, and aid in regular submissions to accreditation by the campus and the entirety of the university.

In general, this paper highlights the analysis, design, development and implementation **ALumni Unified Management and Network Information System**. With the system in place, it is anticipated to provide valuable information, reduce erratic information, and significantly improve the records-safekeeping of the Alumni office subjected to use the **ALUMNI App**.

The research project generally aimed to design and development of the **ALUMNI App** that streamlines the processes involved in the monitoring and updating of the CSU Aparri alumni data, employment history, the assessment of the relevance and applicability, and assessment of the school and related services. It specifically aimed to analyze and plan an alumnus tracking and management system using popular and secured web development tools and scalable database tool. It further aimed to test and evaluate the extend of compliance of the developed application to the indicators of the ISO 25010:2011 as well as the usability and acceptability following the aspects of the Unified Theory of Acceptability and Usability of Technology (UTAUT).

2. Materials and Methods

As a developmental study, the project implemented a descriptive-developmental research design. The design science process was maximized during the development mode. The descriptive design applied the tools to determine the assessment of the extent of compliance to ISO 25010:2011 and the indicators of the usability and acceptability thru the Unified Theory of Usability and Acceptability of Technology. The project commenced with a thorough project kickoff meeting, defining clear goals, scope, and success criteria, while assembling a dedicated project team. Through collaborative workshops with administrators, alumni, and stakeholders, we meticulously gathered detailed functional and non-functional requirements, prioritizing features based on user needs and institutional goals.

2.1 Local of the Study

The study was conducted at Cagayan State University – Aparri Campus, Maura, Aparri, Cagayan, Philippines (9M22+P3C, Aparri, Cagayan). All the development efforts were done at Cagayan State University at Aparri.

2.2 Respondents and Sampling Technique

For the study, the CEO, 8 Alumni coordinators of the Colleges, 1 Campus Alumni coordinator, and the officers of the CSUA Alumni Association. 10 IT Experts were sources of data, involved to assess the system's technical aspects.

2.3. Data Collection Instruments and Procedures

Survey instruments to elicit participants' share of information and dissemination. Ethical considerations in the different aspects of the current research project shall be highly implemented. This includes confidentiality and application of the provisions of Data Privacy Act of 2012 in the analysis phase, design and development phase, as well as in the evaluation phase. Adhering to the university policies for data collection and storage, the system to be developed shall likewise be of high regard. The assessment or survey-questionnaires emphasized the extent of compliance to ISO 25010:2011 by IT experts, while indicators along usability and acceptability of the Unified Theory of Acceptability and Usability of Technology by key stakeholders or residents. Document analysis provided options to analyze various forms, templates, and reports. Observation checklist was used to understand process flow and procedures. Interview guide questions to alumni were able to provide clearer picture of the process flows. Communications and consent thru the office of the deans signaled various data collection, analysis, and development activities.

2.4. Analysis of the Data/ Statistical Treatment

Weighted means, standard deviations, and other descriptive tools were used. With the assessment aspect of the use of ALUMNI App, weighted means and standard deviations were utilized.

3. Results and Discussion

This The design and development of the Alumni Unified Management and Network Information System was done using secured web technologies including the Laravel Framework, CSS3, HTML5, AJAX, and MySQL as its database. The developed ALUMNI App features a functional module for the different services it offers for its stakeholders including the dashboard menu to display all the relevance and acceptability of current employment, assessment of school and related factors of alumni of Cagayan State University Aparri Campus.

Specifically, the features of the ALUMNI App include:

- a. Find my account which will be the first step to find the name of an alumna or alumnus.
- b. A sign-in feature which will be the gateway to authorized users to use the functions of the system upon verify by the administrator.
- c. A dashboard also added for easier to select courses per program, and view total number of graduates, total employed, number of male and female.
- d. The Alumni menu which showcases the add alumni button where the alumni can add or edit his/her name.
- e. The User Profile is also available for users to edit/modify their information and even modify their passwords.

Figure 1: Find my Account

Figure 2: Sign-in feature

Figure 3: The Dashboard

Figure 4: The Alumni Menu

Figure 5: The User Profile

Conclusion

The alumni app serves as a valuable platform for fostering connections, enhancing professional networking, and promoting engagement among former students and their alma mater. By integrating modern technology and user-friendly functionalities, it provides an effective solution for keeping alumni involved while benefiting current students, faculty members, and the administration.

Based on the results, the following items are recommended:

1. To improve the app's interface and usability to ensure seamless navigation and accessibility for all users.
2. To ensure compliance with data protection regulations to safeguard users' personal information.
3. Collaborate with the campus and colleges to encourage alumni to register and actively participate in the app's activities.

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